

ACTIVITIES OF A MODERN TRAINER IN THE PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM

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Annotation: The article presents the results of a study based on literary sources that study the personality of a coach, his pedagogical skills in the modern system and the role of a coach in shaping the personality of a young athlete.

Key words: personality of the coach, pedagogical skill, pedagogical activity, athletes.

Introduction. One of the most important conditions for the renewal and development of modern society is to improve the quality of training of teachers and trainers, which includes deep professional competence, high general culture and social activity [1, 3, 4]. This is precisely what the overall strategy of modern teacher education presupposes. The important role assigned to a coach in society is also determined by the fact that his life attitudes and value orientations are realized in two main directions:

- firstly, as personally significant for oneself;
- secondly, as necessary for fruitful pedagogical activity.

The current level of development of mass sports puts forward ever-increasing demands on the personality of the leader of a children's sports team and his skill [2]. The problem of a coach's pedagogical skill is one of the central ones in the theory and practice of sports pedagogy. According to the requirements, pedagogy considers the pedagogical skill of a coach as a socio-pedagogical phenomenon [5].

The problem of pedagogical skills of a children's sports team coach has still not been practically developed. Only certain aspects of the activities of a children's

coach have been the subject of special research in recent years. However, only by understanding the psychological structure of the trainer's pedagogical activity and the processes of formation of his personality, it is possible to create a scientifically based theory of his skill [7, 8, 9]. It is especially important to solve this problem for trainers at the beginning of their activities, when an attitude towards the chosen specialty is formed and its social essence is realized.

There are a number of objective and subjective shortcomings in the practice of trainers. The vast majority of public trainers begin to work without special training, and the content of short-term courses and seminars is determined only by the needs of practical activity [6, 10, 11]. The lack of a clear methodology for professional training and self-education of public trainers, the lack of educational and methodological textbooks, and the low qualifications of methodologists reduce the effectiveness of the work of teachers of children's sports teams. All this makes relevant the tasks of theoretical and practical substantiation of the problems of pedagogical skills of trainers [12, 13].

The pedagogical skill of a coach is a set of skills necessary for the productive solution of pedagogical problems. Pedagogical skill is a method of action that is based on a set of knowledge, skills, inclinations and abilities and is consciously implemented by a trainer in a pedagogical situation [15, 16].

The skill of a trainer is complex, due to the need to solve an endless series of logical interrelated pedagogical problems. The pedagogical task involves the trainer's understanding of the ultimate goal of his activity and ways of solving strategic, tactical and operational tasks that are correlated with each other in the process of educational and extracurricular activities. The method for solving the problem should reflect all components of the trainer [14, 17].

At different levels of a trainer's skill, different components of the structure of his activity become leading. Therefore, it is very important to find out what difficulties trainers experience at different stages of their work and outline ways to overcome them, comparing the activities of beginners and experienced trainers.

An important component of a coach's skill is his skill in shaping the personality of a young athlete. The process of personality formation can be represented as the functioning of a complex dynamic system, the interaction of elements of which is determined by the leading role and authority of the coach, the influence of the external environment, and the state of the teenager. Therefore, the skill of a coach in this process should be considered as a purposeful system of personality qualities, regulation of relationships determined by the main forms of a teenager's life, identifying changes in the development of his personality and determining the optimal means of influencing it [18, 19].

One of the conditions for improving pedagogical skills is the organic unity of the theoretical, methodological and practical activities of the trainer. This presupposes deep and comprehensive mastery of the theory and methods of physical education, psychological and pedagogical knowledge, consolidation of theoretical knowledge in a particular sport and the development of practical skills on their basis, testing and testing of knowledge and skills in independent pedagogical work, development of an attitude towards further improvement through self-education . The loss of any of these links leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of the coach. Mastery in the upbringing and training of young athletes requires a high degree of development of pedagogical knowledge, skills and abilities. If any component in the structure of a coach's pedagogical activity is insufficiently developed, pedagogical influences turn out to be ineffective.

The skill levels of coaches guide them toward a gradual expansion and deepening of the range of sports and pedagogical skills. Therefore, the coach needs to achieve detailed processing of each skill at all levels of training and education of young athletes, determining effective criteria for solving problems, correlating his own skills with standard ones, mastering functional knowledge, consolidating knowledge and developing the ability to operate with it in practical activities.

The organization of pedagogical influence places high demands on the creativity of the trainer. Trainers, as a rule, have a fairly deep understanding of the characteristics

of the object of influence, but do not sufficiently comprehend the features of their own creative nature (appearance, facial expressions, expression, expressive capabilities), that is, they are not always able to productively manage their psychophysiological apparatus [20].

One of the specific creative problems in a coach's activity is the division of the educational and training process into stages that form a dynamic system that is regulated by constantly emerging pedagogical tasks, which requires the coach to be able to quickly navigate changing circumstances, analyze, and make this or that decision.

A coach will be able to perform his functions in the pedagogical system only if he has professional knowledge, skills, and abilities, as well as certain personality qualities.

Yes, successful management of the educational process depends on a number of psychological conditions, the most important of which we consider: clarity and clarity of the goal of forming the athlete's personality, planning the formation of the personality in a sports team, studying the results of the process of forming the athlete's personality, psychological and pedagogical preparedness, personality traits and the authority of the coach [3, 5].

Clarity of the purpose of educational work helps to find and successfully use the means and methods necessary for implementation. Having clarified the requirements for the formation of an athlete's personality, the coach will be able to more purposefully develop his personality in the process of educational and training sessions. The coach needs to correctly determine the tasks of theoretical and practical training of athletes, the relationship between the general and the special in the formation of their personality.

One of the main conditions for the success of managing the educational process is its planning, which ensures the internal interconnection of all aspects of this process, subordination of its content and means to achieve the main goal - the formation of the athlete's personality.

Management of the educational process is impossible without studying its results, knowledge of the characteristics of the formation of the athlete's personality, analysis of the conditions of training, education, practice, determination of the possibilities and prospects for developing the moral, volitional and physical qualities of the athlete.

Thus, the management of the educational process puts forward certain requirements for the personality of the coach himself. Thus, psychological and pedagogical preparedness allows him to more accurately determine the goal and means of educational work, take into account the characteristics of the individual and collective psychology of athletes, quickly find the right approach to them, taking into account their personal qualities, skillfully build relationships, influence the mood and general attitude towards sport in general[5].

Conclusions. Theoretical analysis of literary sources showed that the study of the pedagogical skills of a coach is a relevant topic for many studies today. In addition to a high level of knowledge in the field of biological and psychological processes, the coach needs a complex of pedagogical and special abilities.

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